

Bringing the Public Back to Our Observatories!

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Nestled atop towering mountain summits, astronomical observatories serve as gateways to the cosmos, allowing scientists to peer into the depths of space and unravel the mysteries of the Universe. While these observatories are typically reserved for cutting-edge research, it's important that their doors are open to the public. Allowing the public to visit large astronomical observatories at mountain summits not only fosters a sense of awe and wonder but also plays a crucial role in education, inspiration, and the promotion of scientific literacy. Arranging visits to a working research facility located at a high-altitude and remote location, however, can be challenging.

Our partner and funding agency, the National Science Foundation (NSF), encourages broad participation and diversity in US research. One goal of NSF is to broaden participation in science and engineering on the part of underrepresented groups, including women, minorities, Indigenous peoples, persons with disabilities, and veterans. Another goal is to encourage broad understanding of the astronomical sciences by a diverse population of scientists, policymakers, educators, and the public. Astronomy is considered to be a gateway science. This presents an opportunity to use its wide appeal to the public to encourage interests in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM). An important component of NSF's NOIRLab's Broader Impacts

program is the public, open, and (mostly) free public visits, catering especially to previously underserved audiences in our locations.

Guided observatory tours help to demystify complex astronomical concepts, making them accessible to people of all ages. Visiting the vast expanse of a mountain summit observatory has a profound impact on individuals. The experience fosters a sense of humility and connection to the cosmos. These moments of awe and wonder can inspire individuals, particularly the younger generation, to pursue careers in STEM. It is an opportunity for people to engage with scientists, ask questions, and gain insights into the latest discoveries. This direct interaction fosters a sense of curiosity and critical thinking, empowering individuals to better understand and appreciate the scientific process.

After the creation of NOIRLab on 1 October 2019, NOIRLab's Communications, Education & Engagement planned to upgrade and streamline the operations of the [public visits program](#). The goals of this program are to attract, facilitate, and implement free visits by 5000 public visitors a year to the summits and base facilities in Hawai'i and Chile and paid visits by 16,000 public visitors a year to Kitt Peak National Observatory in Arizona. In addition, we host at least 50 [media visits](#) a year to all sites combined and assist the site directors

in hosting VIP visits. All of this must be done in compliance with safety rules and other regulations.

One of the cornerstones of our [community engagement](#) activities is to create an appreciation for the role of NOIRLab in astronomy and to share the sense of belonging to the places where the observatories are located. These important communities include the Tohono O'odham Nation in Arizona, the local and native Hawaiians in Hawai'i, and the local communities around our observatories in Chile. We want the local communities to feel welcome and to share the magnificent facilities that are used to carry out the science.

Stewardship and Sustainability

Being a good steward of both Earth and the sky is a [core principle of NOIRLab](#). This commitment begins in our local host communities in [Arizona, Chile, and Hawai'i](#). NOIRLab operates its facilities in an economically, socially, and environmentally sustainable manner. The visits are a unique chance to share information about [NOIRLab's Environmental Sustainability Program](#). Steps towards [sustainability](#) include shrinking the [carbon footprint](#) of our activities, preserving dark skies, and being attentive to the lands that host our facilities.

A goal for any observatory is to [preserve the dark skies](#) in its surrounding areas. The visiting public,

Figure 1: Aerial view of Kitt Peak National Observatory. Credit: KPNO/NOIRLab/AURA/NSF/P. Marenfeld

local authorities, and the media can learn about the importance of avoiding light pollution in order to continue the scientific research, which in turn helps support the local economy.

Safety

A strong safety culture at NOIRLab and AURA makes safety our single most important issue, requiring effective communication between the local directors, safety experts, visits team, and local science operations teams. To provide visits at the four summits and three base facilities, NOIRLab-wide procedures and rules were developed and discussed with all stakeholders at the individual observatories; with NOIRLab’s safety officers; with stakeholders at our managing agency, AURA; and with the Services at NOIRLab. Manuals for the daytime and nighttime guides were written, and a training program was set up.

Inviting laypeople to mountain summits ranging from 2200 meters to 4300 meters in altitude involves considerable attention to safety, increasing in importance with the elevation. The ascent to the observatory exposes visitors to a

reduction in atmospheric pressure, which can result in altitude sickness, typically involving headache, dizziness, and lightheadedness. The sunlight at the observatories can

be exceptionally bright, and the temperature significantly lower than at the base and with high winds. And there’s usually no fuel or food available in the vicinity.

Figure 2: The first public visitors to Kitt Peak National Observatory after the pandemic and the June 2022 Contreras Fire. Credit: KPNO/NOIRLab/NSF/AURA

Public Visits to Observatories

There are two types of public visits at NOIRLab: free visits to NOIRLab’s Hawai’i and Chile locations and fee-based visits to Kitt Peak National Observatory (KPNO), which contribute to offsetting most of the costs of the Kitt Peak Visitor Center (KPVC), approximately \$1 million/year.

Kitt Peak National Observatory, Tucson, Arizona, USA

Two of the highest priorities of the KPNO public visits are to work closely with the Tohono O’odham Nation community in the definition of the educational offerings and to keep the site open to free visits from the Tohono O’odham Nation tribal members, who own the land the observatory is located on.

At Kitt Peak the new [Windows Center](#) beginning in late 2024 will provide interactive exhibits and educational programs, and visitors will experience

Figure 3: The Gemini North telescope (middle) on Maunakea at sunset. The ridge is dotted with about a hundred visitors enjoying the almost otherworldly experience on the dormant volcano. Credit: International Gemini Observatory/NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/J. Chu

the iconic architecture of the McMath-Pierce Solar Telescope and unique live daytime solar disk viewing, interactive spectroscopy, and nighttime viewing of bright objects.

Private vehicles can be driven all the way to the summit on the scenic AZ State Road 386, which was repaired after the June 2022 Contreras Fire.

A [website](#) aimed at visitors provides information and access to booking. Guests can also purchase walk-in tickets if there is availability. The fee-based tickets at KPNO are sold via the established ticket provider [Eventbrite](#), which has a standard credit card payment portal in place that respects all local and national regulations.

Daytime Tours: The KPVC offers three daily 1.5-hour-long daytime tours to the 2.1-meter Telescope, the 4-meter Nicholas U. Mayall Telescope, and the McMath-Pierce Telescope. More than 20 telescope domes can be seen during the tours, and close-up access to one of them is possible. The tours focus on the important contemporary astronomy research

being done at Kitt Peak, but some elements from KPNO's impressive history are also touched upon. Important cultural, biological, and geological elements of Kitt Peak's impressive "Sky Island" are shared with the guests.

Nightly Observing Program (NOP): Every evening the 4.5-hour Nightly Observing Program is offered. This involves getting to know the constellations, using binoculars, and observing with one of the KPVC telescopes.

Overnight Telescope Observing Program (OTOP): The Overnight Telescope Observing Program is offered on eight nights a month around the New Moon and gives up to four guests the full observatory experience of using one of the four KPVC telescopes. The guests eat with the astronomers and get to sleep in one of the astronomers' dorms after a long (or short) night of observing.

Hawai'i and Chile Observatories

Visits to the Chile and Hawai'i locations are free. For the free visits, a

[booking system](#) was developed using a consolidated process with one entry point for booking. The system implements all the rules and procedures agreed with all stakeholders, while still making it as simple to book the tickets as possible.

Gemini North: The most majestic of the free visit locations is arguably the Gemini North telescope on Maunakea (MK). Because of its elevation at 4200 meters (nearly 14,000 feet) above sea level, these visits require some preparation. Only 4-wheel-drive vehicles are allowed on the mountain road leading up to the summit. At the Hale Pohaku 2800-meter (9200 foot) level, a one-hour stop is made to acclimatize visitors to the altitude and provide a safety briefing describing precautions and typical symptoms of altitude sickness.

Visitors are able to see the control room where the astronomers work, the coating chamber to learn more about the engineering that supports astronomy research, and the telescope with the 8.2-meter-diameter mirror and instruments that capture the light from distant galaxies and stars.

Figure 4: View of Cerro Pachón with the SOAR Telescope in the foreground, Gemini South in the middle and the Simonyi Survey Telescope at the Vera C. Rubin Observatory at the back. Credit: Rubin Observatory/NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/T. Matsopoulos

Cerro Tololo and Cerro Pachón, Chile: The weekly visits to Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory (CTIO) and Cerro Pachón in Chile are the most popular NOIRLab visits. At Cerro Tololo a total of more than 40 smaller or larger telescopes can be seen from either afar or up close. The Tololo tours have taken place for decades and are well known to Chileans and

tourists. The Cerro Pachón visit alternates between the Gemini South telescope and the SOAR Telescope. When the construction is finished, the visits will include parts of the Vera C. Rubin Observatory.

In Chile, driving safety rules were recently upgraded, which means that the public can no longer drive their

own cars on the gravel roads to the two summits. Instead, outsourced bus transport has been introduced, which has increased visitor safety.

Visits to Base Facilities

The three base facilities in Tucson, Arizona (HQ); La Serena, Chile; and Hilo, Hawai'i (HBF), are opened to the

Figure 5: Visitors to Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory in Chile. Credit: CTIO/NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/L. Opazo

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public once or twice a month. Visitors are able to learn how engineers build telescopes and astronomers perform astronomical observations remotely, to talk about astronomy and local cultures, and to ask questions about NOIRLab.

Moving Forward

The pandemic provided an unusual challenge for face-to-face events and visits at NOIRLab. As a result of the July 2022 Contreras Fire at KPNO, the

Arizona Department of Transportation had to close the KPNO access road to the public until September 2023.

The first several months of slow ramping-up of the NOIRLab public visits have been a significant success, with lots of excited guests and mostly five-star reviews. For a new consolidated organization like NOIRLab, the combined visits program has provided a chance to work across the organization and involve more than 30 stakeholders in the organization.

Figure 6: The NOIRLab Headquarters base facility in Tucson, Arizona. Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/P. Horálek

Figure 7: The number of visitors to NOIRLab's facilities before (left), during (middle), and after the COVID-19 pandemic (right). The number of visitors is still picking up, especially at Kitt Peak National Observatory. Not all NOIRLab sites were open to public visitors before the pandemic.